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The Relationship between Succession Planning and Performance Management on Employee Engagement in the Egyptian Banking Sector

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Abstract

Considerable research has linked succession planning (SP), and performance management (PM) practices to employees' engagement (EE), but little research has concentrated on how succession planning, and performance management enhances employees' engagement. The objective of this study is to examine the relationship between succession planning, performance management on employees' engagement in the banking industry in Egypt. The research employed a quantitative approach, with questionnaires distributed among 392 respondents working in the banking sector in Egypt, to test hypotheses using appropriate statistical techniques. From the data analysis, the outcomes of this research indicate that succession planning, and performance management programs and practices are found to have significant relationships on employees' engagement. The present study is critical in helping banks management, Human Resources professionals, and people managers to formulate a strategic, and proactive succession planning, and performance management programs and practices to build cohesive working environments while enhancing employees' engagement among banking professionals. Moreover, the outcomes support the management and Human Resources professionals to be proactively ready with sustainable, and stronger pool of candidates for their existing and future roles while keeping employees engaged to deliver their current jobs performance requirements, that all supports in achieving both financial and non-financial business goals.

Keywords: HRM practices, Career management, Succession planning, Performance management, Employees' engagement, Banks.

1. Introduction to the research

Historically and as stated by Henri Fayol, the French pioneer of management history, back in 1916, that any enterprise management has the responsibility to ensure its workforce stability for longer periods. Otherwise, it will be forced to hire unqualified and unprepared employees. Career management (CM) is the most critical aspect for any professional individual, who seek their organizational support, to avail the right tools during their career designing, and planning phases, to achieve their ultimate career aspirations efficiently. Moreover, CM positive outcomes would increase employees' competitiveness in the work place, have better transferable skills, and be more capable to increase their employment chances. When career plans are eventually achieved, it provides employees with the essential levels of resilience, confidence, empowerment, realizing better financial income, whilst being more ready for the future, to deliver what is strategically required from any organization, and most importantly, increases their engagement in the workplace (Spurk et al., 2018). Similarly, and as the employee is the corner stone for any firm, (whether it provides products or services, multinational or domestic, large or small), managing and supporting their staff careers is tremendously critical for all organizations to maintain its competitive position in the current fierce, and uncertain business environments. Optimize their resources to the maximum, whereas focusing on

keeping the continuity of the business without any disruptions is key (Armstrong-Stassen & Ursel, 2009). It is worth noting that the key and distinguished employees leave their organizations, if they are not able to broaden their knowledge and achieve their career aspirational goals. Therefore, they move to achieve it elsewhere, they transfer their companies' clients base, knowledge and expertise to their new organizations, which significantly put any business in a rectified risk that sometimes can't be rectified (Bayu & Wahyuningtyas, 2022).

Having said so, theoretically and pragmatically, it is fundamental for any association to keep its employees highly engaged and motivated, sometimes, more than market competition, to carry on their responsibilities efficiently, and to deliver the agreed objectives successfully. Employees need to feel the sense of belonging, and see their career progresses while they are working in their companies, when realized, employers will get the required engagement and motivational levels. Nevertheless, employees' interpretations of their current and future work meaning do not only depend on the degree of the organizational support in providing them with the right career progression programs, but it is also built based on the real opportunities giving to them to attain their career aspirations (Xueling, 2017). Therefore, literature reviews have addressed CM, its dimensions and EE and its measurements separately; few studies captured the relation direction especially in a practical manner; whereas, rare studies analyzed this relation, while investigating CM main variables, including succession planning (SP), and performance management (PM) (Donohue & Tham, 2019). Furthermore, pragmatically, literature reviews have addressed several questions related to CM, but very little knowledge is captured related to what happens on the ground, and why it happens regarding career outcomes and its efficient execution methodologies, as it is usually based on career initiatives or programs, that are disconnected from the organizational goals, or because they mainly focus on organizational objectives with isolation from employees' future career objective, that all eventually, affects employee engagement (EE) (Hernaes et al., 2019).

Similarly, CM and EE are found to be essential dilemmas that need to be addressed transparently and efficiently. In other words, it is very costly for any organization to let employees go away, and it is more aching to see them dis-engaged till leaving for not having the right career progression opportunities or insufficient transparency when it comes to direct or in-appropriate appointments for the vacant positions, instead of moving them to achieve their career aspirational goals (Finkelstein et al., 2017). Consequently, and as per the pre-mentioned, the purpose of this research is to compile, review, and empirically investigate the relationship between succession planning, and performance management (as independent variables) and employee engagement (as a dependent variable). This research will focus on employees working in the banking sector in Egypt while considering, and testing the relationship between each of the dimensions of the CM and EE.

2. Research Problem:

(Ralevic et al., 2015) highlighted the issue of lacking the connectivity and cohesiveness between the HR practices, as it should be designed based on employees' career aspirational goals, being the key success factor for fostering the organizational performance, and its sustainable success. The study has highlighted that this will help as fundamental ground for building solid organizational culture, encourages positive employees' behaviors, and enhances their engagement levels. Additionally, the HR activities should not solely focus on the existing vacancies requirements, the robust recruitment and selection processes should consider employees' future career aspirational goals, based on the actual organizational available, and delivered opportunities. When both organizational and employees' mutual benefits achieved, SP programs and PM outcomes are positively realized. Consequently, higher engagement levels attained, and eventually better overall organizational outcomes. Correspondingly, another complimenting view has captured that SP and PM practices, and its realistic programs is a dilemma, that has direct effect in increasing EE, and satisfaction levels when planned, designed, reached its pre-settled and agreed outcomes properly. Managing SP and PM efficiently will not only serve the current organizational success or differentiation strategies, it will also help in maintaining its stability, and better operational resilience for longer terms. The corner stone of having successful CM offerings would start with creating vibrant individualized career paths, to be reinforced by wide organizational supportive tools starting from SP, with clearer, and more objective PM

system. The study has also captured the importance of organizational transparency, and communication related to SP and PM practices, being the main tools for increasing engagement levels. It became necessary than ever before to build continuous, long term, and sustainable efforts on all associated HR and management practices, to be able to improve their employees' engagement levels (Mi & Ali, 2024).

Nowadays, the fierce business environment and increased competition has emphasized the role of PM systems, as a necessary tool for better organizational effectiveness that will eventually lead to better delivered products or services, and higher customer satisfaction levels. The study has defined PM as the main central system that is positively and directly linked with EE levels. Furthermore, the study has emphasized on the cruciality of the fairness aspect related to PM practices, discussions, and final objective outcomes, that all have direct relationship with enhancing employees' feelings of emotional commitment, being more powered, have the sense of belong, which all lead to higher engagement and satisfaction levels (Gruman & Saks, 2011). (Mone & London, 2018) have similarly seized the direct positive relation between having robust PM system and EE levels, and its negative impacts when lacking fair and objective PM system. The characteristics of the solid PM cycle were also tackled in this study, starting with employees understanding of the overall organizational goals, and how it is broken down to their business functions, and daily activities, what are the required deliverables and its quality standards. Additionally, the study emphasized on the ongoing and open feedback communication channels, employees being able to design their actual self-assessment, and evaluations of their outcomes versus the required objectives, while the most critical element in fostering the engagement is having aligned goals. That all results in increasing the sense of being valued, committed, and highly engaged.

Based on the above-mentioned, the research problem statement is crystalized as “the purpose of this study is to compile, review and, empirically, investigate the relation between succession planning, and performance management on employees' engagement, while testing the effect of both SP, and PM dimensions on employees' engagement as per literature, in Egypt banking industry.

3. Research Objectives:

The main objective of this research is to examine and explore the relationship between succession planning, and performance management on employees' engagement, in the banking industry in Egypt while taking into account its SP, PM, and EE variables dimensions as per literature. In this setting, and as relevant to the research, the following objectives were recognized:

- 3.1 Contributing to the “HR research” and “management research” by bringing in the two variables of “SP”, and “PM”, their relationships with the other variable “employees' engagement”.
- 3.2 Highlighting the necessity of investigating the relationship between SP, PM, its practices, and employees' engagement, in Egypt banking industry.

4. Conceptual Model:

Figure 1 Conceptual Model

5. Literature Review

5.1 Career Management

Historically, the management author Frederic Taylor has put a good foundation of CM, with a clear starting point, he emphasized on the criticality of having role specialization with a ladder movement within specific field, where employees are required to perform certain roles within the organization (Taylor., 1911). Consequently, they can go further in other higher grading positions based on seniority level, and the required experience, as a result, they can eventually achieve their professional progression, career aspirational goals and the required levels of engagement (Abele & Spurk, 2009). Another relatively recent research highlighted the shift in the second half of the 20th century based on several other factors starting from socioeconomic changes, the dynamic changes in consumer's preferences, shifts in their demands, globalization, as well as the rapid changes in the business environments, and the required technological advancements, especially in the banking industry. Having said so, all have necessitated the organizations to be more understanding, as well as, designing mutual beneficial strategies and initiatives for their staff (Purcell & Hutchinson, 2007). Likewise, having genuine commitment, embedding it in all organizational strategies, with focus on building a strong culture and better physical environment while being more flexible towards their employee CM approaches became crucial. Moreover, further shifts took place, as staff started to be more self-driven, progression started to be horizontal and not only vertical. Maximizing the efforts on efficient career programs start with attracting, developing, engaging talents till retaining them will lead to higher employee attachment, generating positive work and cultural environment, as well as a stronger financial and non-financial outcome, especially in banking where financial numbers changes, and that can be well seen immensely (Kidd & Smewing, 2001).

Oxford English Dictionary, 2015 edition captures that career is the (person's course or progress through life or distinct portion of life, the series of jobs that a person has in a particular specialization with diversified responsibilities as the time passes) (Oxford,2015). Likewise, historically, CM notion has never been common, it was mainly recognized as the first job choice, later, it was perceived as the core aspect of the employment agreement, which comes with diversified HR programs, however, it is crucial for employees as well as their employers (Xueling, 2017). Meanwhile, said CM programs should tie it all, starting with individuals' careers aspirations, designing the policies related, and also covers any strategic challenges including but not limited to the technological advances, and the necessity of adopting it, while focusing on the required productivity, and desired outcomes at organizational level. On the contrary, the CM concept is dissimilar to any other social science, it is not owned or created by one theory, it is mixed combination of psychological, sociological, and organizational behavior theories, while emphasizing on the individual's accumulation of both educational and hands on experiences (Arthur et al., 1989). Kotter being one of the management and leadership gurus has equally reflected the sociological interpretation, being an individual personality type would shape his or her career professional type. A more realistic, and aggressive behavior character, with stronger physical capabilities would highly choose agricultural, driving or alike occupations, while a more social individual would prefer counseling or teaching career. Therefore, other positions that requires high communication and selling skills would grasp people with imaginative profile, controversy, a conservative individual would choose a banking administrative position (Sonnenfeld & Kotter, 1982).

The contemporary literature review highlights the criticality of the employee owning his or her career journey, as Feldman has highlighted, staff are the best to understand, and decide how they can adjust its pre-designed CM goals, and its millstones, while considering any challenging, and unexpected people related activities as re-structuring, downsizing, mergers or acquisitions based on organizations streamlining or simplifying aspirations (Ng & Feldman, 2013). Having said so, all forced implementing HR practices than ever before, to be more advisor and strategic business partner, while working on complementing staff career aspirations, studies have shown that career satisfaction directly, and indirectly ventures individuals, and organizational outcomes with higher engagement, lower turnover, creating stronger organizational culture, and strong competencies foundation. Thus, it is all reflected and linked in the conservation of resources theory (COR), where it settles that, any employee is naturally motivated to sustain same level, if

not more resources are availed, to avoid any future risks that might arise, they always act based on the available resources to achieve their goals (Halbesleben et al., 2014).

The banking sector, its requirements, from skills perspective have been evolving after the global financial crisis, and as captured in a recent literature, that studied all associated research from the year 2000 to 2021, with initial review of 197 journals, and ended with 47 publications, that are most relevant to the banking, and majority were in Asia, Middle East and Africa. The research utilized a qualitative data that are converted to numerical results, with a coding tool, research summarizes, that banking was shifted from being a complex operational environment, to be more technological based, capitalizes on artificial intelligence, big data, and early risk mitigation concepts. Hence, all forced banks, to have more strong CM strategies, with better pragmatical, and efficient retention programs, more transparent, and genuine commitment from the bank. CM programs should be designed and linked, to meet staff career expectations, and avoid demotivating them, the research concluded, that CM is one of the highest, scored factors, that has efficient positive relation on EE in banks (Theodorsson et al., 2022). Equally, in Pakistan banking industry, that has witnessed significant growth, especially over the last 20 years, with fierce competition between banks on their pricing of products and services to their consumers, a questionnaire with a Likert scale research was conducted on 450 different banks employees confirmed same relation, when bankers get strong support, well-designed HR programs, with greater job flexibility, that supported by strong leadership management, it increases staff belonging levels and reduces leaving intentions. The analysis reflected 65 % positive strong correlation and responses confirming the same (Hunjra et al., 2011).

5.2 Succession Planning

Historically, Leibman has stated that SP definition was initially perceived as a replacement planning. When Marriot hotel started to re-shape the awareness around hospitality sector, to be more seen as luxurious leisure service provider, their concept also changed towards their staff development and SP programs, to be able to deliver the required excellent services to their guests (Leibman et al., 1996). Equally and when all technological companies were forced to provide, and support organizations with more innovatory technological tools, for their staff to work from home or anywhere swiftly, that was not a normal business. Consequently, telecommunication companies had to support on the SP conceptional shift journey. Likewise, SP new concept adoption was a must, especially, with the new thoughts around the more diversified workforces, looking at hiring female versus male ratios, being more inclusive environment, ensuring having different age groups, and nationalities (Moquin et al., 2019). Furthermore, with the more required flatten organizations, allowing for better and faster decision making, empowerment and delegation practices, and the additional required social responsibilities to be delivered to the communities they are operating in. All forced corporations to change their concept about SP, not only to stabilize the organization but also, to build the right tools, be more competitive, and proactive to what is happening in its industry (K.Siambi, 2022). Similarly, SP brings a thoughtful and systemic process, and efforts to be executed by any firm to ensure its stability, continuous existence, and develop this corporate knowledge while encouraging its most critical asset, the human capital. This research mainly focusses on building efficient SP including CM practices, L&D, coaching and mentorship programs, with special focus on the high potential internal employees, who can take future higher roles, which is normally designed per specialized area of expertise. All emerging the corporates to achieve it to ensure its presence, while increasing their ability in managing the business with better and more stringent risk mitigation metrics (Gabriel et al., 2020).

Having pitfalls in any company, or deterioration of outcomes is not one-person or Leader responsibility, it is the failure of a companywide system, and practices. Hence, going to hire someone externally, is an official confession of failure, it informs the society that this company did not work on hiring best people from the beginning, no career development plans were designed to make their employees ready for the future, while lacking all developmental aspects that they had to work on proactively. Historically, back in 1970, the General Electrical Company has adopted the critical career crossroads concept, they developed a model called the leadership pipeline, to understand the leadership requirements across the company. Basically, the model consists of six- passage starting from managing self, and ending with the enterprise manager, the model highlighted the responsibilities for each phase, opportunities, and challenges that go in-

parallel with anyone personal life journey, the main objective was also for GE to be ready for the future, and be able to mitigate any risks and achieve its strategic outcomes. The research further emphasized that, the first entry for young employees would start with spending their first few years in a specific position or field like sales or marketing, where they are required to manage own self, doing what is required from them, when they perform well demonstrating their reliability, commitment, and high-quality deliverables, then, they are considered for promotions. Therefore, when showing better collaboration levels, good values, and team working capabilities, they get additional activities, be promoted to the first line managerial level. The ending phase was the skills, that was mainly focused on leadership traits of being visionary Leader with more strategic outcomes, while focusing more on companywide linked objectives and not functional anymore, setting the directions, review the performance, and take immediate proactive actions (Drotter & Charan, 2001).

As the HR guru, Dessler highlights, SP is the process of confirming, and ensuring that organization have the proper pipeline of supply required for its future senior positions, that would start with identifying the critical roles for the company, recognizing potential second line for it, assessing their development gaps while following up on it, to ensure it closure efficiently (Dessler, 2005). Furthermore, the author has later identified SP as it is the process articulating how the company would backfill it is critical or senior positions, when it became vacant, then, how to design their SP systems, not the other way around (Dessler, 2017). Worth noting that, any planning activity outcomes might not be achieved as it was originally designed and thought of, no one knows the future, and what would happen in 1 to 2 years or more, however, what HR function along with the managers would do if key positions employees' departure suddenly or if there are some retirement cases in the coming few years, this is a key question, to plan, and be ready to respond to it. On the other hand, any strategic management decision including mergers, acquisition, or re-structuring, for better efficiencies, or downsizing would bring necessity of assessing people capabilities, to keep the best for the future, that might be much better opportunity for some people, where HR and management should focus and start designing some plans around main key questions related. How many positions needs to be fulfilled and when, what is the time to backfill said roles, what is the organizational history in actual terms to fulfill from within, and what is the successful ratio when filled internally (Rothwell, 2010). Moreover, the classical research highlighted that SP concept, and its success is largely based on leadership traits and concepts, all were tackled, and evolved in the last 200 years including Greta Man, behavioral, contingency, transactional and transformational leadership theories, Furthermore, and as illustrated in the below table 1, Gordon has put a roadmap that is called PREPGO representing SP framework to promote for organizational sustainability (Gordon & Overbey, 2018).

Table 1 – Succession planning framework to promote organizational sustainability: PREPGO

(Gordon & Overbey, 2018)

	Definitions	Strategies
P: Planning	Design proactive measures to begin SP early on, and to have the right talent ready to move into short term or long-term higher, leadership or strategic positions, that will lead to smooth transitions as current Leaders leave and new Leaders take over.	Plan preemptively and develop through talent management and recruitment strategies that are focused on bringing in future potential successors, who have the necessary competencies. Planning should also consider the number, and types of positions needed for future leadership or key positions. Consequently, designing L&D programs should be based on the existing staff qualifications and skills versus future roles requirements, while frequently examining current staff development to close any developmental gaps.
R: Recruiting	Leaders promoting and preparing for the needs of their institution, by searching for replacements, who can cope with higher levels of stress, make positive impacts on staff, have strong emotional intelligence, and be able to handle politically sensitive situations.	Promote and prepare for the needs of the company by encouraging, facilitating, and attracting employees, who are committed to the organization educational improvement, and would remain for longer tenures.
E:	Retaining and promoting employees to boost	Search for employees who are rising stars, self-driven,

Empowering	morale and engagement.	ambitious, desire growth, want to be part of the team, and who can understand the trajectory of the organization. Current Leaders must share their SP for transparency, for staff to understand what is in it for them, and to be able to close any required development gaps.
P: Preparing	Training and coaching employees to lead any growth or transformational programs designed, to promote the organization and move it to greater heights.	Build relationships and foster change through motivational, supportive, and recognition means. Creating internal leadership programs, to be sponsored by existing Leaders, to maximize the desired efficient outcomes.
G: Guiding	Pairing skilled and experienced employees, who can help in guiding, and mentoring potential staff for future leadership positions, and who can also assist with retention of employees.	Ensure that the agreed mentors and mentees share a common background, make certain appropriate expectations. Both mentor and mentee should design clear and objective goals, make certain mentors share real-world knowledge, arrange for career support mechanisms, systems, and programs across the organization that complement same development journeys.
O: Off to work	New Leaders smoothly transition into their new leadership roles.	New Leaders continue the SP steps in PREPGO ensuring recruitment, empowerment, preparation, and guidance of future Leaders.

Likewise, Gandhi describes that SP is a strategic direction, to ensure that the company got the required skills and knowledge to sustain its business, and be more competitive, while having the accessibility to strong pool of skills when needed. The research highlights that a tailored work experience journeys should be designed, with necessity to be more relevant to the more senior and strategic roles requirements, thus potential staff can take it eventually and efficiently, in case of any senior member departure. Although, preparing staff with the leadership traits, having social intelligence capabilities, got the ability to empower and motivate other people is key. Nevertheless, enhancing their communication and presentation skills is equally needed. Similarly, when organizations build efficient SP system that is communicated across all organizational levels, employees will understand it well, be more engaged in shaping the programs, and they will ensure its efficient application and success. Equally, staff can help in the journey by delivering in-house technical or soft skills courses, to close any required developmental gaps, facilitate any related requirements, mitigate any hurdles, and come up with innovatory solutions to make it happen (Gandhi & Kumar, 2014). In other words, literature has further re-emphasized that current leadership and incumbents of the critical positions, should regularly assess their existing pipeline of employees, who can fit the future leadership positions versus the organizational future needs. The SP should be mainly driven from the required organizational goals and its execution tools and metrics, that will be achieved at all levels, the research has captured that several HR strategies are needed like the exit interviews, reflecting the real gaps at organizational level, while Leaders should embed the outcomes from the interviews in their plans for management consideration, the HR plans should be realistic, relevant, achievable and inclusive of all current employees and company development gaps, the outcomes will give the company the actual readiness levels, as some will be ready to take senior roles immediately, others will be ready on the short term, or on longer term basis (Wilson, 2018).

5.3 Performance Management

PM system was instigated during the 18th century, when Wei Dynasty detected the performance of his cotton mill workers in Scotland using silent monitors; but that was not objective enough. Further shift took place in 1930 based on the operational efficiency principle, which was linked with the ROI model. It is crucial, for any organization, to measure its employees' work achievements versus company's strategic objectives, that creates stronger link between employees and their employers. Having said so, PM acts as a strong foundation for L&D needs for each employee, which helps in enhancing the overall organizational performance, and staff engagement while enriching people capabilities. Likewise, the well-structured performance system helps in avoiding the spread of any undesirable biasness or untruth stories in the working environment (Rao et al., 2020). Similarly, companies believe in the PM and its associated processes as the corner stone in building strong and efficient CM outcomes have better outcomes, PM would start with staff setting their objectives, in line with the company strategic goals, till conducting fair assessment for appraising them, based on their actual deliverables. Building on the same, the desired outcome beyond such

actions is to have fairness and consistency, to clear any uncertainties or biasness in the workplace (Memon et al., 2019). Mangipudi has defined that PM as the logical, and sequential process of evaluating employees, teams, and functional departments across the whole organization, to ensure its alignment and commitment to the pre-agreed and settled goals. It gives great tool for the management to explore any current or future development gaps that affect the overall vision, and performance of the company, whereas solving any conflicts; PM would be a great base for designing employees L&D programs. On the other hand, the system should also be founded, to encourage employees' creativity, with strong conduct and values-based culture. PM is simply the road map for the organizational long-term success or failure; the high performers will lead the change, and make the exceptional accomplishments. Underperformers, who are reluctant to participate in any activities, if they are not managed properly to be developed by relevant PM processes, they will be demotivated, and dis-engaged, that will diminish the company deliverables, performance quality, and might put the company in countless reputational risks (Mangipudi et al., 2019).

Furthermore, giving fair, transparent and clear feedback for each employee is essential; on the other hand, disagreements between managers and their staff related to the evaluation of their work deliverables and its outcomes should be regularly discussed, monitored, regularly tracked, and closed to avoid any demotivational attitudes or work disengagement patterns (Yang et al., 2018). Having said so, several PM associated aspects must be tested, to ensure successful implementation of PM systems including: designing efficient, two ways and frequent giving and receiving feedback processes, that should take place throughout the year; setting and documenting clear and agreed objectives along with its outcomes and its required quality standards is key, while designing strong acknowledgment process from employees on their managers' assessment regarding their work outcomes is an essential step. Having a ranking model, to motivate high performers and work on underperformers development is vital, the systems should be focusing on competency-based models, to avoid any subjectivity while it should be designed based on clear organizational objectives. Such objectives should be broken down according to each business line related goals that might be financial or non-financial. PM should also include behavioral rating scale, this is imperative, to ensure having the right values and behavioral requirements set by the organization, to demonstrate the right solid culture (SHRM, 2022). The management guru, Peter Drucker has detailed the management by objectives (MBO) concept, being a critical element for all management functions. That would start from top management, who should understand their business main objectives, and its required outcomes, then integrate all company related functional activities in one holistic view. Subsequently, and once all company employees understand and agree on these objectives, both parties will be more satisfied and aligned, in this case, no need for the frequent reminders from management on the objectives, staff will have the self-control and motivational concepts to preform adequately. It is crucial for all parties to understand what should be achieved and its required quality measurements? Having said so, the MBO process would typically broken-down in three phases, first would be setting clear objectives, coming from the overall company main goals, second, the agreement and enrollment of the designed objectives, while continuously having feedbacks on the delivered outcomes to correct any deviations from what is required, and that should take place across the whole organization. Third, would be the overall holistic combination of all efforts in one shape (Drucker 1954).

The CEOs do not work anymore solely, they should be working closely with the management team, to collaboratively design the overall company strategies, creating related policies and procedures, broken down by each function, empowerment and delegation metrics and its responsibilities, although, having efficient and measurable outcomes should be clear for all. Also, the organizational goals might be different based on the business nature and its complexity; however, the essence is the same. The jobs nature, and its final output is different within same company, it differs based on the products and services delivered to each company's client base, as an example, one product might take long years of manufacturing like an airplane, and others might produce several product units per day. Having said so, the required goals should be mentioned in each employee balance scorecard, while taking into consideration future considerations or challenges if any. The concept of managing teams by objectives is challenging for any people Leader, however, this is a core element of any Leader's job (Starbuck, 2018). Equally, each line manager is responsible to discuss his team objectives with their line managers, to ensure that communication flow goes

both ways, to ensure higher management commitment, empowerment, delegation, and buy in when needed. This commitment and alignment is crucial to facilitate any challenges, or to mitigate any potential risks throughout the journey. Having said so, the most crucial element in this process is each employee self-commitment, and control while taking responsibility, if that apprehended, better career opportunities will arise (Maciariello, 2016). The performance system should include combination of several elements including: the organizational goals, the ongoing two ways constructive feedback process, while considering current and future opportunities to reward the staff.

Doerr has captured that the objectives and key results (OKR) model, that emphasized on what matters most, that will take the organization behind the daily details, and its routine. John Doerr has focused more on clearly defined goals, and its associated outcomes while making the whole process transparent for all employees, which will generally embed a high-performance working culture, and enhances the required engagement levels sustainably. Additionally, deciding on the long-term organizational goals is vital, the objectives of each function should be clear, that might include any new initiatives, programs, simplification of existing processes or policies, however, the management should prioritize the more critical areas, any significant challenges to overcome, and to maximize the outcome from available resources. Nevertheless, communicating the changes to the whole organization at first is key, to ensure all people understanding and alignment. By turn, and when that achieved properly, there is a strong base for any performance assessment, per team and individually. The below table 2 illustrates the difference between the management by objective (MBO) and intelligent OKR (Doerr, 2018).

Table 2 – MBOs vs. OKRs

(Doerr, 2018)

MBOs	Intelligent OKR
“What”	“What” and “How”
Annual	Quarterly or Monthly
Private and Siloed	Public and Transparent
Top-down	Bottom-up or Sideways
Tied to Compensation	Mostly Divorced from Compensation
Risk Averse	Aggressive and Aspirational

Additionally, and as the business environments became more challenging and complex, the PM has to be more structured, supported by software applications that provide comprehensive analytical features and detailed reporting tools. A lot of great technological tools were developed, introduced, and deployed in several organizations. Employees became more empowered than ever before, they can go on their Mobiles, add their objectives, send it to their managers for review, track it, amend it, send and receive frequent detailed feedbacks on their work progress, where they can finally reflect their deliverables and any feedbacks on it instantly (Doerr, 2018). Likewise, same criticality was re-emphasized, that PM software applications became a must, as it gives all managers an immediate empowerment; to set goals of their teams while pre-discussing it in advance, track the progression on frequent basis, to correct any pitfalls instantly. With the live giving and receiving feedback feature, that closed the whole performance cycle efficiently. Said applications would be also tied with L&D, rewards and SP tools, for the best outcome to employees, and eventually to the organization (Holznienkemper, 2024).

5.4 Employee Engagement

Albrecht historically defined the EE as staff being fully attached noticeably, mentally, emotionally to their work place, and their current positions. That was later tweaked, to define EE by the staff who is seen by other people got the sense of meaningful, purpose, complete energy, and persistent towards achieving the organizational strategic objectives. EE is the positive mind status demonstrated when staff are fulfilling their work-related responsibilities, particularly when they are dealing with internal or external job-related stakeholders, with strong commitment, dedication, and excitement while delivering their job requirements and interacting with others. Also, the staff engagement main drivers are based on the established organizational support, work environment, culture norms; job related supporting tools, and their personal characteristics. Having said so, the organizational understanding of these key drivers is necessary for better planning, designing, actual, and efficient execution of EE enhancement tools, and that is why staff engagement might fluctuate, from time to time or from task to task, based on the level of support given to them (Albrecht, 2010). Equally, EE is defined as the positive contentment of work-related aspects tied with the positive state of mind, which is seen and reflected in the level of enthusiasm, commitment, and adaptability within the work environment. Hence, EE can be better achieved with the direct managers empowerment and delegation to their team members, while giving continuous constructive feedback, and providing them with the right career and development opportunities for better realized direct outcomes. As a result, the firm can increase the mental and emotional attachment to it, while increasing staff sense of belonging being a critical engagement tool, which by turn decreases turnover rates and enhances the operational resilience requirements, and final strategic outcomes. Studies have also captured the dependent variable of each individual persona, including being open for new experiences, the need for an emotional stability, while demonstrating high levels of eagerness, vigor and willingness to challenge them, which are all vital predictors for positive EE reflection in the work place setting (Albrecht & Marty, 2017).

Similarly, EE was generally conceptualized, and tied with the level of commitment, contribution, and awareness that employee would show towards the job responsibilities, and participation in the overall organizational goals while motivating peers and other work colleagues. The engaged employees usually take ownership, display proactive approaches, and getting it done with high quality outcomes. Engagement is always great tool for any company to survive against its rivals, as human capital is the most valuable strength they got, it is one of the major factors to measure any organization resilience. When EE is there, it enhances organizational strong conduct culture and values, in addition to achieving high levels of collaborative corporate culture working patterns (J., 2014). Furthermore, it is extensively acknowledged, that any organization wins with its highly competent employees. Accordingly, it is crucial for any organization to keep its employees engaged and focused, to deliver their pre-settled objectives, and to also maintain its hiring, and L&D costs efficient. Worth noting that employees leave for not finding the right career paths, recognitions or appreciation on their work deliverables and dedication. In fact, employees need to feel the sense of belonging while progressing with their career aspirational aims (Pandita & Ray, 2018). Complementing with the same views, consistent CM practices have great effects on EE and that increases their loyalty. Additionally, retaining employees versus external hirings save a lot of costs while more importantly avoiding deteriorating engagement levels for remaining staff. Hence, CM is a great tool to keep employees in their organizations for longer tenures as it represents a great benefit to the staff, and that ensures the organization's sustainability and success (Ali & Mehreen, 2019).

Furthermore, work attachment can be seen when any challenging tasks are required, that reflects staff capabilities to bring their full energy into the work place, positive engagement, drive more innovative ideas for specific challenging work dilemmas. Higher engagement is recognized when there is strong connection between the corporate objectives, culture and its values that matches staff personality traits and conduct. Having said so, organizations should have more diversified HR practices, and programs that address the diversified staff experiences, and career aspirations across the firm. Also, other critical elements including L&D opportunities should be designed to help in achieving staff career aspirational aims, support them in their SP journeys which will drive better engagement and satisfaction levels, additionally, the provided development opportunities should support in embedding the required empowerment, and delegation practices (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). However, the literature has emphasized on the critical role of Leaders in

achieving better EE levels, based on their general management, and communication style. Leaders should have clear visions and strategies, while being open, and transparent with their teams. People managers should be more coaches, with strong focus and support to their teams (Welch, 2011).

The delivery of an employee normal duties is the minimum level of their work belonging. However, the strong engagement is measured when they are more team oriented, go extra miles without management requesting. Engaged staff come with solutions, think about other colleagues and how they can support them; they pass credit to other people, while avoid blaming others. Hence, engagement can be measured via questionnaires, focus groups, and staff surveys or interviews (SHRM, 2022). Likewise, some factors can be measured to test the engagement in the work place with specific set of questions to cover the elements related to the working environment like the leadership style in the firm, and collaborative practices across teams. Other EE measurement tools might include the accessible organizational tools related to CM and training opportunities while determining its relevancy to staff aspirations is vital, the strength of rewards system, the applied policies company wide, the introduced well-being initiatives, and the overall adoption and staff feedbacks around those practices (J., 2014). However, another literature shows that Leaders can only achieve the desired engagement levels when they demonstrate clearer vision of the company with frequent communication to their teams, while providing the required emotional support, and most importantly, show recognition for employees' contribution in the archived business outcomes. Leaders' behavior is key whether it is authentic, charismatic or ethical; all increases or decreases engagement levels (Carasco-Saul et al., 2014).

5.5 Relationship between Succession Planning, Performance Management, and Employees Engagement

Montgomery has highlighted that the HR programs should come up with non-traditional supporting tools, to enhance staff engagement and increases motivational levels. EE can be enhanced by attending events or learning conferences, conducted industry awareness sessions or appraising them through newspapers or social media channels. Encouraging staff in general in achieving their career aspirational goals is great organization sign to its staff. Furthermore, EE tools would embed establishing internal L&D schools, getting short term assignments or temporary projects as it allows greater levels of empowerment and delegation, with the new tasks assigned to them beside their normal work responsibilities, the additional learning journeys would give staff much better social status, that emotionally engages their satisfaction and engagement levels (Montgomery, 2002). Likewise, efficient HR strategies would require more integrated, comprehensive systems, policies, and procedures that all complement each other. Clear evaluation and success measurement criteria are critically needed, that is helpful for the company to understand the existing levels of engagement, and to also understand where they should be landing. Organizations should build frequent follow-up mechanism, to ensure that all programs and initiatives are taking place as it was designed, and if efficiently implemented or not, if not, timely correction plans are needed. Likewise, the company can start with the selection process and its related assessment exams, to test the candidate's willingness, pro-activity, and eagerness to learn new tasks, predicating their interactions in working teams while assessing their values, behavioral aspects and conduct. Later, L&D opportunities should be designed, and availed to staff while assessing their involvements, and engagement in it, when positive, more can be delivered. The staff voice is a great channel to get staff views and recommendations for the future, all would be positive supporting tools to build a robust effective and successful working culture when staff voice matters, and their recommendations are key (Guest, 2014).

The management guru Porter has illustrated the strong relationship between staff past job experience, and the archived engagement levels; however, very little knowledge has covered employees' expectations towards their future career development and desired movements, as their past experience is definitely different from their future goals. Also, worth noting that future career aspirations are based on individual differences, views and beliefs, it is proven that individuals reflect their current emotions, reactions and decisions based on their future ambition and perception of its key success factors. Correspondingly, staff can interpret their unmet job expectations, by the difference between what they actually experience versus what they initially thought about their future jobs and careers. This concept was covered in several classical

literature review including Porter (1975), who highlighted that there is an efficient relationship between employee career and job satisfaction, on one hand, and the engagement level, on the other hand, ending with them leaving their organizations if they are not satisfied (Maden et al., 2016). Yang has further reflected that other studies described the definition of career plateau as a stagnant phase where employees do not see any further career progression opportunities to move forward including promotions or moving laterally. When they do not have challenging jobs, it deteriorates EE, commitment, loyalty and satisfaction with higher desires to leave their organizations (Yang et al., 2018).

Likewise, Jiang has highlighted that HR practices, policies, and ways of implementation is one of the main aspects for any staff behavioral act whether it's positive to support the organization or the opposite. Any employee performance is combination of skills, information, values, capabilities, that eventually affect the whole company positivity or destructively. Having said so, the engagement initiatives are key while it should be supported by the overall positive and well-designed HR systems, starting with the selection process to get candidates that suits the organizational values, and conduct culture via assessing their adaptability through situational examples questions till SP to get the higher organizational levels roles fulfilled (Jiang et al., 2012). Also, academic research has proved that the personal growth, proper PM, and L&D opportunities are designed and meant to be engagement tools like having proper feedback discussions on performance that motivate staff more to do extra miles, be more creative, and proactive. Equally, the Manager's coaching concept has also proved same relation in boosting EE, the research captures that these HR valuable resources would build more solid psychological employees and organizational connections, and no staff would like to lose them, unless it is better provided elsewhere. When employees have all supportive resources, they are more emotionally attached, and they would deliver much more than required (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008).

The psychological contract between employees and their companies is described by the beliefs that employees shape; how they understand and perform what is required from them, and what their organizations will provide them in return. It is highly crucial agreement, and firms should give greater attention to it as it forms the base of employees' engagement, when that positively established, it enhances staff actual contributions to a great extent (Low et al., 2016). Also, EE is now seen than ever before, engagement became one of the most important organizational success indicators, which associated with several measurement and evaluation tools like the demonstrated inclusivity degree, the fairness and equity of all HR practices, with more focus on recruitment activities, being a crucial element in the perceived organizational justice when dealing with candidates (O'Connor & Crowley-Henry, 2017). Similarly, strong HR programs create a great organizational fair, care and engagement climate with special focus on career development and its associated activities; however, companies should be providing its employees with actual promotional and transfers opportunities, to show that they are genuine about its employees' career progressing plans (Saks, 2022). On the opposite side and as Harvard research on internal versus external hirings showed that internal candidates are better for the organizations as they understand the culture, they are the best ones who can manage their profit and loss budgets and cost centers. On the other side, externals, which are mainly headhunted, come with much higher price, worth noting that the median pay of an external CEO would be on average \$3.2 million above the internal median average, which force the investors to meet said demand, to manage the business and enhance the share value (Harrell, 2016).

Interestingly, another research has described that the engaged staff are the employees who always go beyond their normal job duties and responsibilities that is more coming from the self-driven concept. The literature went deeper with clear definition about their characteristics describing that they always work with great passion, and that is seen by all internal and external people dealing with them. Engaged employees speak more about their work, its outcomes, and their contributions even in social events, they see the tangible outcomes, they basically follow their passion and not only to obey line have managers to get worked done (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). However, CM remain fundamental, not only for employees to keep them engaged and loyal but also for any organizational success, in order to achieve its desired outcomes including reducing turnover rates; however, designing and executing the right HR programs and its associated policies strengthen the relation when it is there. The organizational programs and support should be continuously and clearly communicated at all levels, including employees' direct managers who should

always elaborate on how these tools are designed to support employees CM and their future aspirational goals. Also, same research investigated CM relation on EE, on 364 Japanese employees who their responses proved the constructive connection between CM, its supported practices by the organization and their employees' satisfaction and engagement levels (Jung & Takeuchi, 2017).

Several researches tackled the link between managing career pathways and business long term objectives, and its strategies success. SP, and PM include the meaning of managing talents, thus, managing employee's career aspirations, especially for staff who showed great potentiality than others. CM involves several employee value proposition (EVP) programs, including designing L&D programs for them; helping employees in tracking their career progress; closing the gaps towards their performance goals, with frequent reassurance that they have future accomplishments, to be archived as they desire. As a result, they feel more engaged and motivated (Pandita & Ray, 2018).

5.6 Conclusion

To conclude, this chapter compile, review, analyze several literature reviews that captures the main research variables definitions, concepts theories and cases with more practical reflections. This is an efficient base for the coming research methodology chapter and the hypotheses development.

6. Research Methodology

6.1 Research Design

The purpose of the research mainly reflects the variables, research population, and the main scope of the research. The purpose can also be both explicit or implicit, should be reflected objectively, while avoiding any biasness or personal views of the researcher.

The purpose of this research is "Exploring the Relationship between Succession Planning, Performance Management and Employee Engagement: Research on Banking Sector in Egypt"

The descriptive approach supports in analyzing associated patterns, while formulating the hypotheses that can be strong guidelines and general plan for the future. This direction is utilized to explore the and how a phenomenon take place as the main aim of the research is exploring the Relationship between Succession Planning, Performance Management and Employee Engagement: Research on Banking Sector in Egypt. Descriptive research is a quantitative research technique that helps the researcher in collating the required measurable data from the population sample and its outcomes statistical analysis.

This research carried out a quantitative approach to test the hypotheses and to answer the research questions. A descriptive correlational design base is used; this is because it is the most relevant method, as the research aims to determine the relationship between SP, PM, and EE besides assessing to which degree this relationship exists in the banking industry in Egypt. Additionally, measuring CM and its dimensions is a challenging topic and a difficult dilemma to manage as employees look more for programs that increase their engagement and retention (Alias et al., 2016). While the lack of career opportunities highly impacts EE and turnover intentions, and it is definitely much better to manage it proactively, to avoid its undesirable effects (Yang et al., 2018). The research will, mainly, tackle the main two independent variables relationship on employees' engagement represented in: SP, and PM.

6.2 Research Population and Sample

The target population includes all white-collar employees in the banking industry in Egypt; other responses with irrelevant criteria will be excluded.

As per Babbie, the sampling frame is the physical representation of all diversified elements from the population of the research (Babbie, 2010). The frame should be illustrative to afford an inclusive list of each element in the population. The researcher reviewed respondents' characteristics to align and ensure the

criteria of the target population are met. In Egypt, all banks are registered under law No. 194 for the year 2020 that stipulates authorizing the CBE to set and execute all related policies for the whole banking sector in Egypt.

The sampling unit and its context are the individual employees working in banks in Egypt.

As per Wang, the sampling is defined as the process of selecting efficient number of the right elements from the target population being an enabler for the research and the researcher, to generalize the results as collating the data from the entire population being the banking sector in Egypt will be unbearable and extremely costly (Wang et al., 2013).

Based on the aforementioned, and also based on Sekaran sample size framework, and as the researcher has precise population frame, information, definition and criteria for the population under scope, the researcher in this research will execute the **non-probability convenience sampling** since each sampling unit and its associated respondents capture an equal chance of being selected as a sample unit. The applied technique is non-probability convenience sampling since the sampling frame is specific and definite population. The population, in scope, has the similarity while achieving the desired generalizability of the research findings to the entire population, which is crucial for the researcher.

The factors affecting deciding on the sample size includes the accuracy desired is called the confidence interval, while the satisfactory and acceptable risk in forecasting the levels of accuracy called the confidence degree. Also, the sample size is based on the volume of erraticism in the targeted population, the time and cost challenges, in addition to the size of the industry and its selected population.

As per Sekaran, as this research is non-probability convenience sampling, and as the banking sector in Egypt include more than 100,000 employees, the data in this research will be collated and analyzed quantitatively from 392 banker, based on Sekaran and Bougie (2016), and also as per Roscoe (1975) who proposed that the rule of thumb for determining the sample size is when sample sizes larger than 30 and less than 500, this is appropriate for most research, the sample will be white-collar individuals working in diversified banks in Egypt. That can represent the population with confidence degree at 95%.

The sample encompassed all employees working in the banking sector in Egypt that included all levels (junior, senior, supervisors, section head, team leader, department head, vice president, and director).

6.3 Data Collection & Measuring Scale

The researcher followed a quantitative approach in conducting this research as this will give the researcher the quantitative questionnaire reflects much broader research as it involves more respondents. It achieves the purpose of having the desired generalization. It is efficient and more simplified in data collection. It provides better objectivity and accuracy of collected data as respondents prefer to have multiple-choice answers.

The questionnaire is utilized for both descriptive and explanatory purposes in the research as it includes efficient criteria based on the clear questions, its relevancy to the studied research and its variables, the right sequential order to attract the interest and willingness of respondents to answer it. The benefits from the questionnaire approach can be briefed as it is a convenient tool for the respondents as it can give them the flexibility to respond where and when they can complete the questionnaire, capitalizing on the technological advancements and its tools as the answers are automatically inserted in spreadsheets, and also in other software applications that all increases the validity and reliability of the data gathered, where it also reduces the risks from any human error interaction in any phase, and reaching out to many respondents with more cost-efficient tools.

The approach for developing this research questionnaire passed through the following sequential phases:

1. The researcher has referred to the previous relevant studies and literature reviews that are related to the main research variables to:
 - a. Specify and identify the main scope and dimensions of each variable.
 - b. Determine the questionnaire that will be used to conduct the research.
2. The questionnaire was sent to all bankers in the Egyptian banking sector to answer it as pilot research to understand the time consumed and get any feedbacks on clarity of the questions and main purpose from the research.

The results will be, statistically, reflected by employing SPSS software. The core finding of this research will be based on investigating the relationship between SP, PM and employees' engagement while assessing the relationship impact.

The following section shows the source of the questionnaire used to measure each variable as illustrated in the literature review, three engagement scales measurements have been (Soane et al., 2012). The researcher will adopt the intellectual, social and affective engagement scale – the ISA model in the questionnaire, along with its associated questions (measuring EE) as captured in the below 3 table summarizing the measuring variables.

Table 3 – Questionnaire source and variable measuring:

Variables	Reference	Measurement Scale
Succession Planning	(Rothwell, 2002)	5-point Likert scale
Performance Management	(Verbeeten, 2008)	5-point Likert scale
Employee Engagement	(Soane et al., 2012)	5-point Likert scale

6.4 Hypotheses Development

SP, being an independent variable, is a crucial aspect in any professional individual career life, and it can immensely affect employees' engagement (the dependent variable) which is vastly required for any business success, resilience and continuity (Bayu & Wahyuningtyas, 2022).

Having said so, the current research can propose the following hypotheses broken down from the main relation. Ali et al. (2019) found that there is a strong positive relationship between SP and employees' engagement, likewise, another research distributed to 300 employees working telecommunication industry in Pakistan, with 250 final collated responses resulted in proofing that there is strong relation between SP and employees' engagement (Gulzar & Durrani, 2014); hence, hypotheses 1 is developed as follows:

H₁: Succession Planning has a significant positive relationship with Employees Engagement.

(Saratun, 2016) has captured the relationship between PM and employees' engagement and proved its strong relation. likewise, according to (Gruman & Saks, 2011), the primary focus to foster employees' engagement is the performance management. Similarly, (Awan et al., 2020), captured there is a strong positive relationship between PM and employees' engagement. Based on the above, hypotheses 2 is posed as follows:

H₂: Performance Management has a substantial positive relationship with Employees Engagement.

7. Statistical Analysis

7.1 Demographics Analysis

7.1.1 Gender

The sample size is (392) three hundred and ninety-two. Table 7.1 reflects the distribution of the sample based on their gender.

Table 7.1 – Gender:

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	247	63%	63%	100%
	Female	145	37%	37%	37%
	Total	392	100	100	

This table reflects that the majority of the respondents were from males representing 63% from the sample with strong female representation as well 37% as diversity is critical in the banking industry in Egypt.

7.1.2 Age

Table 7.2 prescribes the distribution of the sample as per their age.

Table 7.2 – Age:

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	24 - 30 years	109	27.8%	27.8%	27.8%
	31 - 40 years	175	44.6%	44.6%	72.4%
	41 - 50 years	87	22.2%	22.2%	94.6%
	51 years and above	21	5.4%	5.4%	100%
	Total	392	100	100	

This table reflects that almost 45% of the sample falls in the range of 31-40; this indicates that the majority of the sample falls in the middle of the workforce / career journey period.

7.1.3 Management Level

Table 7.3 captures the distribution of the sample as per their management level in their organizations / banks.

Table 7.3 – Management-level distribution:

Management level					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Entry Level	58	14.8%	14.8%	14.8%
	Middle Level Management	220	56.1%	56.1%	70.9%
	Senior Management	114	29.1%	29.1%	100%
	Total	392	100	100	

This table shows that 56% of the sample is the middle management level in their career journey. This indicates that the sample focuses on the second layer in the professional career ladder.

7.2 Internal Consistency Validity

The internal consistency, for the variables, was estimated using the reliability score, Cronbach's alpha, with Cronbach's alpha of .70 representing acceptable reliability (Nunnally, 1978). Likewise, a recent article by (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011) has confirmed same efficient range of percentage. Table 7.4 shows the result of Cronbach analysis.

The internal consistency reliability for the scales of SP (4 items), Performance Management (5 items), and Employees Engagement (9 items), were 0.815, 0.886, and 0.862 respectively. Having said so, all represents high reliability as per (Hinton et al., 2014) guide. Article captured when to consider the scale proper for reliability, as illustrated below:

Table 7.4 – Cronbach's Alpha:

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of items
Succession Planning	0.815	4
Performance Management	0.886	5
Employees Engagement	0.862	9

7.2.1 Normality Test

The researcher carried out a normality test on the gathered data, to check if it is normally disseminated or not using Shapiro-Wilk tests as recommended by Uma Sekaran (Sekaran ,2003). Table 7.5 captures the significance levels of EE, SP, and PM. All are below ($p < .05$), which indicates that said variables are not normally distributed within the sample.

Table 7.5 – Tests of Normality:

Variable	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Employees Engagement	0.973	392	0
Succession Planning	0.961	392	0
Performance Management	0.94	392	0

7.2.2 Correlation Test Analysis

The correlation coefficient (r) can be in the range between -1 and +1, where -1 represents a perfect negative correlation between two variables, and +1 represents a perfect positive correlation between two variables (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

According to Cohen guidelines, this test followed cutoff intervals for the effect size of the correlation coefficient as shown below in Table 7.6; it is divided into 4 intervals (Cohen, 1988; Cohen et al., 2003). Likewise same, correlation was confirmed by (Nolan & Heinzen, 2011; Bosco et al., 2015).

Table 7.6 – Cohen guidelines for effect size interpretation:

Correlation coefficient value (r)	Effect size
$(r) < .1$	Negligible / Very small
$(r) = .1$ to $.3$	Small
$(r) = .3$ to $.5$	Medium
$(r) > .5$	Large

Table 7.7 below illustrates the bivariate test results, and the significance of the correlation on the behavioral intention, since all correlation coefficients among the independent variables are below .7, and according to Pallant (2005) or .9 according to Hair et al. (2010). Having said so, this indicates a probability of the absence of multi-collinearity.

Table 7.7 – Correlations:

		Employees Engagement	Succession Planning	Performance Management	Learning and Development
Employees Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
Succession Planning	Pearson Correlation	.548**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0			
Performance Management	Pearson Correlation	.515**	.637**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

7.2.2.1 Correlation between employee engagement and other variables

The results shown in the above table 7.7 indicates a statistically significant positive correlation between:

1. Employees Engagement and SP, that means a higher Employees Engagement is associated with higher SP in this sample.
 - ✓ The correlation between Employees Engagement and SP is considered to be high since the correlation coefficient ($r = .548$, $p < .000$).
2. Employees Engagement and Performance Management, that means a higher Engagement is associated with higher Performance Management in this sample.
 - ✓ The correlation between Employees Engagement and Performance Management is considered to be high since the correlation coefficient ($r = .515$, $p < .000$).

7.2.3 Regression Analysis

7.2.3.1 Succession Planning & Employees Engagement

H_1 : **Succession Planning** has a significant positive relationship with **Employees Engagement**.

Table 7.8 – Model Summary b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	.548 ^a	0.3	0.299

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Succession Planning
- b. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement

Table 7.9 – ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	49.848	1	49.848	167.444	.000 ^b
	Residual	116.104	390	0.298		
	Total	165.952	391			

- a. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement
b. Predictors: (Constant), Succession Planning

Table 7.10 – Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.299	0.127		18.046	0.000
	Succession Planning	0.445	0.034	0.548	12.94	0.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement

As shown in the above table 7.10, the unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .445$, $p < .001$), which indicates that for every one unit increase in SP, there will be a .445 unit increase in employees' engagement, in case we consider all other variables are constant.

The result above supports (H1) that SP has a significant positive relationship with Employees Engagement in the banking industry in Egypt, where ($B = .445$, $p < .001$), and the model is fit as R^2 of .30.

7.2.3.2 Performance Management & Employees Engagement

H₂: Performance Management has a substantial positive relationship with **Employees Engagement**.

Table 7.11 – Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.515 ^a	0.265	0.263	0.55920

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Management
b. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement

Table 7.12 – ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43.995	1	43.995	140.691	.000 ^b
	Residual	121.957	390	0.313		
	Total	165.952	391			

- a. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement
b. Predictors: (Constant), Performance Management

Table 7.13 – Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.214	0.146		15.199	0.000
	Performance Management	0.449	0.038	0.515	11.861	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employees Engagement

A simple linear regression test was capitalized on, to assess the effect on employees' engagement (outcome variable) based on PM (predictor variable), the results shown in table 7.12 and 7.13 indicates a significant regression equation ($F(1, 390) = 140.691, p < .001$) and R^2 of .265. This R^2 means that 26.5% of the variance in employees' engagement can be explained by the PM.

As shown in the above table 7.13, the unstandardized regression coefficient ($B = .449, p < .001$), which indicates that for every one unit increase in PM, there will be a .449 unit increase in employees' engagement in case we consider all other variables are constant.

The result above supports (H2) that PM has a substantial positive relationship with Employees Engagement in the banking industry in Egypt, where ($B = .449, p < .001$), and the model is fit as R^2 of .265.

The following table 7.14 summarizes the result of the data analysis and the relationship among the different variables using the above captured statistical tools.

Table 7.14 – Summary of the Results

#	The hypothesis	The result
H1	Succession Planning has a significant positive relationship with Employees Engagement	Accepted
H2	Performance Management has a substantial positive relationship with Employees Engagement	Accepted

8. Discussion of the Results

8.1 Hypothesis one: Succession Planning has a significant positive relationship with Employees Engagement

The analysis results interrelated that the SP in this research can explain 30% of the variance in employees' engagement. This relationship between SP and Employees' engagement is significantly positive reflecting that efficient SP programs, the more transparent communications around it, the well-designed execution tools, and actual reflection on employees' career outcomes will increase employees' engagement. Likewise, when researcher statistically excluded all other independent variables including the PM. The SP can explain 29.9% of the variance in employees' engagement. Likewise, the regression coefficient outcome showed that for every one unit increase in the SP personalization, actual reflection and employees' fulfillment, there will be 0.445 units increase in engagement in case the other independent variable is constant.

The results are in line with Bayu & Wahyuningtyas article that confirmed the same relationship highlighting that any organization should certainly working on enhancing their CM programs and its efficient practices that have many implications and negative consequences on any company competitiveness and overall performance. The main research prominence was on the SP strong relationship on engagement for better productivity and higher engagement workforces (Bayu & Wahyuningtyas, 2022). Ali et al. (2019)

has also emphasized on the vital preparations of internal candidates for future leadership roles that have direct, and strong effect on staff engagement and overall organizational effectiveness, where these organizations will have greater employees' commitment and loyalty unlike other companies who did not work on their future potentials.

Gulzar & Durrani have tackled the importance of SP and proved some positive relationship, they articulated that talents awareness and regular updates given to them related to their SP programs, that should be tied with their career aspirational goals have increased their engagement levels and fostered their commitments towards their organizations (Gulzar & Durrani, 2014). Similarly, and complementing same views, and as captured in Rothwell's literature that highlighted the critical role of SP for any organization to ensure its success, continuity, and resilience towards any challenging circumstances in the current or future business environment. Also, SP should have the right focus from organizational leaders, who should create second level of potential talented individuals, while having smooth transitional phases to ensure their success in the new higher and more critical positions. Correspondingly, it was captured that discussing SP with future potentials is key, while discussing their development gaps for efficient closure, that will significantly enhance organizational stability and increase employees' engagement levels (Rothwell, 2010).

8.2 Hypothesis two: Performance Management has a substantial positive relationship with Employees Engagement

The results revealed that the PM in this research can explain 26.5% of the change in employees' engagement. This percentage is significantly positive reflecting that the robust PM systems that starts with employees understanding of overall organizational objectives. To be followed by establishing clear and measurable goals, along with having more frequent discussions on the employees ongoing deliverables, ending with the fair and transparent assessment to their final outcomes, will increase employees' engagement. Additionally, and when researcher included SP, being the other independent variable, both together can explain 34.4% of the variance in employees' engagement. Also, the regression coefficient analysis reflected that every one unit increase in PM, there will be 0.449 units increase in engagement in case all other independent variables constant.

This in line with Saratun research that confirmed the significant role those organizations should play in order to directly enhance their staff engagement levels. The efficient PM system should start with designing, and implementing clear and measurable strategic goals, that should be cascaded down to all employees with the right levels of transparency. When the PM culture is embedded, including the mechanism of giving and receiving feedbacks, that all creates long term successful outcomes that are mainly built on employees' engagement, who can lead the desired operational resilience and organizational sustainability (Saratun, 2016). (Awan et al., 2020) has also captured the criticality of having PM system, as staff should see its reflections on their work outcomes, with fair and transparent methodologies. The research also tied the PM system with several other tools that should be rewarding and recognizing the high performers more. Having the robust and strong governance around PM system, its actual outcomes, along with the frequent communications across the company is a great tool for increasing EE that will lead to an outstanding performance at all organizational levels.

9. Research Future Recommendation

1- Applying this research on some other financial institutions in order to examine the relationship interaction among employees working in the financial sector and not only banks.

2- There is a need to focus on other contextually relevant moderators / mediators within the banking industry in Egypt. That might include the demographics, like the age and length of service, to better analyze the relationship with EE.

10. Conclusion

This research aimed to identify the relationship between SP, PM, and EE. This research is conducted on the banking sector in Egypt. The results capture, and reflect the significant positive relationship between SP, PM and EE. Moreover, succession planning, and performance management have significant positive relationships with EE. The research approached 392 banking employees working in Egypt that covered both genders, all age groups, length of service and managerial levels, asking them for their opinion related to the relationship between SP, PM and EE. Some of the significant findings are listed as follows: A strong, significant correlation was found between the three determining factors of CM (i.e Succession Planning, and Performance Management) and EE, demonstrating that all two hypotheses previously listed in the research are positively proved, thus, engagement of employees working in the banking industry in Egypt are affected by SP, and PM plans. This indicates that banks policies, practices, initiatives, programs, and supportive tools, that help their employees SP, and PM determinants are very critical to apply.

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